

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF TOPICAL SUCRALFATE AND INSULIN DRESSINGS IN DIABETIC FOOT ULCERS

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Abstract

Objective

To compare the effectiveness of 10% sucralfate dressing and topical insulin dressing in promoting wound healing over 28 days

Study design

A prospective, parallel-group, randomized controlled trial.

Place & duration of the study

This research was carried out at Mayo Hospital Lahore for a period of six months.

Methodology

One hundred patients were enrolled, divided into two equal groups. Group A (n = 50) received 10% sucralfate dressing once daily, applied as a uniform layer over the wound bed followed by sterile gauze. Group B (n = 50) received topical insulin dressing, prepared by diluting regular insulin in normal saline and applying via sterile gauze soaked for 15 minutes before securing with standard dressing. Wound areas were measured on Days 1, 7, 14, 21, and 28 using planimetry. Percentage reduction in wound area was primary study endpoint.

Results:

The mean age was 53.2 ± 11.3 years in Group A and 54.7 ± 10.5 years in Group B ($P = 0.49$). In terms of gender distribution, males accounted for 54% (27 patients) in Group A and 56% (28 patients) in Group B ($p = 0.84$). Baseline ulcer size averaged 8.7 ± 2.4 cm² in Group A and 8.6 ± 2.1 cm² in Group B ($P = 0.82$). Mean reduction in wound size was found to be significantly higher in the Insulin Group ($36.7\% \pm 0.81$) as compared to the Sucralfate Group ($31.9\% \pm 0.84$), with p -value < 0.001 .

Conclusion:

Insulin dressing showed approximately 5% greater percentage reduction compared to sucralfate. These findings highlight insulin as a promising therapeutic agent for DFU management.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic foot ulcers are a frequent and serious complication associated with long-term, poorly controlled diabetes mellitus. Among the roughly 537

million individuals globally living with diabetes, approximately 19% to 34% are expected to develop a diabetic foot ulcer during their lifetime.^{1,2}

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are among the most severe complications associated with diabetes mellitus. They typically arise due to nerve damage, problems with small blood vessels, and impaired immune cell activity.³ The persistent nature of DFUs presents significant difficulties for healthcare providers, often resulting in infections, hospital stays, and the potential need for amputation if not properly treated.⁴

Approximately one-fifth of individuals who experience a diabetic foot ulcer will eventually need to undergo amputation of the lower limb, which can be a minor procedure below the ankle or a major one above the ankle, or both types. Additionally, within a year of their initial diagnosis of a diabetic foot ulcer, about 10% of these patients will pass away.^{5,6}

Numerous topical approaches have been explored to enhance the healing process, with sucralfate and insulin-based dressings emerging as particularly effective options. Insulin plays a crucial role by stimulating fibroblast growth, facilitating keratinocyte movement, encouraging new blood vessel formation, and boosting collagen production. Sucralfate is a complex compound consisting of an aluminum hydroxide salt combined with sucrose octa sulfate, a disaccharide. It is primarily administered orally to treat gastrointestinal ulcers. Recent studies suggest it may also facilitate skin wound healing. The mechanism involves enhancing the production of growth factors, notably fibroblast growth factor (FGF), which is vital for new blood vessel formation and the growth of dermal fibroblasts and keratinocytes. Additionally, sucralfate stimulates the secretion of cytokines such as interleukin-1 (IL-1) and interleukin-6 (IL-6), supports the development of granulation tissue, and thereby accelerates the healing process of ulcers.^{7,8}

Despite individual evidence supporting both agents, comparative clinical data remain limited. This study addresses this gap by evaluating wound healing outcomes in patients treated with sucralfate versus insulin dressings.

Materials and methods:

This study was designed as a prospective, parallel-group, randomized controlled trial conducted at a tertiary care teaching hospital with a specialized

diabetic foot clinic. A total of 100 patients with diabetic foot ulcers were enrolled following strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. Participants were randomly allocated into two groups using a computer-generated randomization list in a 1:1 ratio. Allocation concealment was ensured through sealed, opaque, sequentially numbered envelopes prepared by an independent staff member not involved in treatment or assessment.

Group A (n = 50) received 10% sucralfate dressing once daily, applied as a uniform layer over the wound bed followed by sterile gauze. Group B (n = 50) received topical insulin dressing, prepared by diluting regular insulin in normal saline and applying via sterile gauze soaked for 15 minutes before securing with standard dressing. No additional topical agents were used in either group.

Blinding was partially implemented. Clinicians and participants could not be blinded due to visible differences in dressings; however, outcome assessors responsible for wound area measurements were blinded to treatment allocation to minimize detection bias.

Inclusion criteria: adults aged 18–80 years, type 1 or type 2 diabetes mellitus, single diabetic foot ulcer (Wagner grade I–II), ulcer duration 2 weeks to 3 months, and adequate peripheral perfusion. Exclusion criteria: Wagner grade \geq III, osteomyelitis, severe peripheral arterial disease (ABI $<$ 0.7), systemic infection requiring IV antibiotics, immunosuppressive therapy, dialysis-dependent renal failure, multiple ulcers, or allergy to sucralfate or insulin.

Wound area assessment used validated planimetric tracing: sterile transparent film placed over the wound, edges traced, transferred to 1 mm² graph paper, and area computed in cm². Measurements were obtained on Days 1, 7, 14, 21, and 28. Clinical photographs documented healing progression.

The primary outcome was the percentage reduction in wound area from baseline at 28-day follow-up.

Data were compiled in SPSS v25 software. A comparison of mean percentage reduction in wound size was performed using an independent-samples t-test, with a p-value \leq 0.05 considered significant.

Results:

The baseline characteristics of the study patients in both Group A (N=50) and Group B (N=50) were comparable. The mean age was 53.2 ± 11.3 years in Group A and 54.7 ± 10.5 years in Group B ($P = 0.49$). In terms of gender distribution, males accounted for 54% (27 patients) in Group A and 56% (28 patients) in Group B, while females comprised 46% (23 patients) and 44% (22 patients) in Group A and Group B, respectively ($P = 0.84$). Regarding smoking status, 26% (13 patients) of Group A and 24% (12 patients) of Group B were smokers, whereas non-smokers constituted 74% (37 patients) and 76% (38 patients) in Group A and Group B, respectively ($P = 0.81$). The mean BMI was 27.3 ± 3.5 kg/m² in Group A and 27.8 ± 3.8 kg/m²

in Group B ($P = 0.49$). Baseline ulcer size averaged 8.7 ± 2.4 cm² in Group A and 8.6 ± 2.1 cm² in Group B ($P = 0.82$). Overall, there were no statistically significant differences between the two groups in any of the baseline variables (Table 1).

Both treatment groups demonstrated wound healing progression across the 28-day follow-up. But mean reduction in wound size was found to be significantly higher in the Group B ($36.7\% \pm 0.81$) as compared to the Group A ($31.9\% \pm 0.84$), after performing the independent T-test (Table 2).

Healing curve patterns revealed more consistent downward trends in insulin-treated patients. Figures below illustrate comparative healing trajectories (Figure 1).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Study Patients.

Variables	Group A (N=50)	Group B (N=50)	P-value
Age (Years)	53.2±11.3	54.7±10.5	0.49
Gender (%)			
Male	27 (54%)	28 (56%)	0.84
Female	23 (46%)	22 (44%)	
Smoking Status (%)			
Smoker	13 (26%)	12 (24%)	0.81
Non-Smoker	37 (74%)	38 (76%)	
BMI (Kg/m ²)	27.3±3.5	27.8±3.8	0.49
Baseline Ulcer Size (cm ²)	8.7±2.4	8.6±2.1	0.82

Table 2. Comparison of Study Outcomes.

Variables	Group A (N=50)	Group B (N=50)	P-value
Mean reduction in wound size (%)	31.9% ± 0.84	36.7% ± 0.81	< 0.001

Figure 1: Mean wound area over time in both groups.

Discussion:

Diabetes has emerged as a significant health crisis in Pakistan, ranking first among nations with the highest rates of the disease, with a prevalence rate of 31%, and this prevalence will rise to 34% in 2045.⁹ The condition and its complications impose a substantial socioeconomic burden on a developing country like Pakistan. The prevalence of diabetes, glucose intolerance, and related complications is notably high in such settings. Patients with diabetes face a risk of amputation that is 15 times greater than that of non-diabetics; however, many of these amputations could be avoided through early treatment, proper foot care education, and effective blood sugar management.¹⁰

This study provides comparative clinical insight into the wound healing effects of topical sucralfate and insulin dressings in diabetic foot ulcers. While both treatments demonstrated significant healing, insulin resulted in approximately 5% greater percentage reduction in wound area. This finding aligns with previous research that highlights insulin's potent effects on wound biology.^{11, 12} Insulin enhances keratinocyte mobility, fibroblast proliferation, angiogenesis, and collagen deposition—mechanisms essential for wound contraction and re-epithelialization. Additionally, insulin stabilizes

hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF-1 α), improving angiogenesis in hypoxic tissue.¹³ These biological mechanisms likely contributed to the more rapid wound contraction observed in Group B.

In comparison, sucralfate primarily promotes healing by encouraging the release of growth factors such as FGF, IL-1, and IL-6, and by supporting the development of granulation tissue. While it is effective, the regenerative process triggered by sucralfate appears less vigorous than the multifaceted biological actions of insulin. The healing patterns observed in patients treated with sucralfate varied more widely, whereas those receiving insulin demonstrated more consistent decline in healing curves.¹⁴

This study's results align with previous international research indicating that insulin dressings offer better healing outcomes than traditional treatments.^{15, 16} While sucralfate can be effective, especially for promoting granulation, insulin's wider biological effects may make it more appropriate for quickly decreasing the size of wounds.

Even a modest 5% increase in healing rates can have significant clinical benefits, such as lowering the chances of hospitalization, infection, and the need for amputation. Insulin-based dressings are cost-effective and readily accessible, which makes them particularly useful in resource-limited healthcare environments like Pakistan. To thoroughly assess their long-term effectiveness, including rates of

recurrence and complete wound closure, larger studies across multiple centers with prolonged follow-up are essential.

Conclusion:

Both sucralfate and insulin dressings significantly promote wound healing in diabetic foot ulcers. However, topical insulin demonstrates superior percentage reduction and more consistent healing trajectories. Its cost-effectiveness, availability, and biological benefits make it a strong candidate for DFU treatment protocols.

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